

TECHNIQUES OF WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL AREAS

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ABSTRACT:

Sustainable development is synonymous to maintenance of productivity of natural resources and maintenance of ecological equilibrium. Sustainable development has become a widely recognized goal for human society ever since deteriorating environmental conditions in many parts of the world indicate that its sustainability may be at stake. Water is an essential component of all the dimensions of sustainable development. Moreover 68 % of Indian population lives in villages and thus the development of our villages is of critical importance for the economic development of the country. Proper management of natural resources like water, forest, land etc through People's participation and initiative along with complimentary and social awareness in society forms the basis of progress of the nation. Effective and efficient management of water plays a key role in human welfare and therefore has emerged as an urgent global concern. At the ground level, specifically in the villages, Problem & solution diagram, Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) are important methods to understand the real needs of the villagers and to identify the water related problems. In addition to this, various water management approaches such as watershed development, water purification, waste water management and rain water harvesting are practical solutions to the water related problems encountered in recent times in rural areas. Such solutions play an important role in maintaining the ecological balance as well as the economic development of the country.

KEY WORDS: Problem and Solution Diagram, Participatory Rural Appraisal, Watershed Development, water Purification, Rain water Harvesting.

INTRODUCTION :

In the present scenario it is realized that sustainable development is synonymous to maintenance of productivity of natural resources and maintenance of ecological equilibrium. Kushwaha and et al. [1] noted that the concept of sustainable development has received much needed impetus after the Rio Conference in June 1992, mainly through the 27 principles on sustainable development and the action plan called Agenda 21 (UNCED, United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, Rio de Janeiro, 3–14 June 1992). The approach was followed up in a big way during the World Summit on Sustainable Development in 2002 at Johannesburg. The Summit re-emphasized the need for strengthening the three pillars of sustainable development, viz. economy, society and the Environment { FIG. 1 }.

The water resources forms an appropriate unit which links all these three components and has a direct bearing on human lives. Water is the resource that sustains all life on earth and is a key element of sustainable development. It is essential if human beings are to enjoy healthy and safe lives or realize social and economic development. Ecosystems are also inextricably linked with water. Historically, water had been regarded as an infinite resource. However, humans are dependent on a mere fraction of one percent of the earth's freshwater—that found in lakes, rivers, and ground water aquifers—as that water is the only freshwater which is readily accessible. As population growth and economic expansion accelerated and intensified the use and abuse of water resources over the past few decades, a greater and greater imbalance between water availability and water demand has resulted. This imbalance has brought a veritable crisis with regard to water in many regions of the world.

Water is fundamental to life, livelihood, food security and sustainable development. It is impossible to imagine world without water. As

per National Water Policy 2012, Ministry Of Water Resources, Government of India; India has more than 18 % of the world's population, but has only 4% of world's renewable water resources and 2.4% of world's land area. Of the water resources on earth only 3.0 % of water is in the fresh form and two-thirds of the freshwater is locked up in ice caps and glaciers [2], Of the remaining one percent, a fifth is in remote, inaccessible areas and much seasonal rainfall in monsoonal deluges and floods cannot easily be used. At present only about 0.08 percent of all the world's fresh water [3]{FIG.2} is exploited by mankind in ever increasing demand for sanitation, drinking, manufacturing, leisure and agriculture.

Groundwater is the major source of water in our country with 85% of the population dependent on it [4] but the average availability of water is reducing steadily with the growing population. Fig. 3 shows the decline in water resource per capita of various regions of the world.

Figure 3: Decline in Water Resource Per Capita (1950-2025)

These facts clearly reflect that in present scenario water management is necessary. According to the United Nation Environment Programme India will become a water stressed nation by the year 2025 and the demand of water will increased from 541 billion cubic meters in the year 2000 to 1072 billion cubic meter in the year 2050. Father of the Nation, Mahatma

Gandhi has stated that India is a land of villages. Moreover 68% of the total population of India lives in the villages and thus development of our villages is of critical importance for the economic development of the country. Agriculture sector has majorly contributed in the economic development of the nation. In villages maximum water is utilized for domestic purpose and farm irrigation. Water Resources Development Board [5] has estimated that in our country 83% of water is used for irrigation purpose and the rest water is used for domestic, industrial and other purposes. This paper helps in understanding the need of water management at village level to eradicate poverty through increase in the agriculture production, provide income generating opportunities, for good health and for the perspective of economic development of the country. Some simple methods which are used to overcome the water related problems of rural India are discussed in the paper.

METHODS:

Since independence, rural development schemes were discussed and formulated at the district, state and central level without the participation of the people. This ignores the local issues and the requirement of the particular area. As a result, these cost intensive rural development schemes were unable to achieve their objectives. To overcome this lacuna standard methods have been taken at villages. In order to solve the specific problem of the village the very first step is to identify the problem correctly. For this purpose, the methods used are Participatory Rural Appraisal, Problem cause and solution diagram and Questionnaire survey at village level.

1. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA)- It is a procedure enlists the participation of the people involved in the developmental schemes being carried out in the villages. This procedure which has now become the key document for any rural developmental work ensures the people understanding of their problems and help in devising solutions that can be implemented by them. People's participation in rural projects increases their scope, satiability and success rate. The rapid spread and adoption of the methodology led to issues of quality [6]. Different simple steps used to conduct PRA are formulation of action plan, preparation of agro eco system map, enterprise map, transact map, prepare livelihood analysis and capture individual technical knowledge to gather information about the geographic, topographic, economic and social

conditions such as water resources, water storage, major crops, irrigation facilities, yield, agricultural production of the concerned village.

2. Problem and solution diagram - Another commonly used method is to prepare problem diagram: the problem diagram is a root cause analysis system. The process involves the formation of various branches/causes of the root cause of the one problem and then a solution diagram for the same problem has been made theoretically. Practical implementation of the solutions given in the solution tree provides the complete solution of the concerned problems.
3. Questionnaire-In addition to PRA and problem and solution tree another adopted method is Questionnaire for village survey. Questionnaire is a list of survey questions asked to respondents, and designed to extract specific information. It serves four basic purposes: to (1) collect the appropriate data, (2) make data comparable and amenable to analysis, (3) minimize bias in formulating and asking question, and (4) to make questions engaging and varied. Water management questionnaire contains the information related to the villages and villagers such as name of the village, population, number of farm families, availability of infrastructure , educational facilities, type of drainage system, average crop productivity, Number of traditional occupation, irrigation facilities etc.

These are the basic approaches to identify the actual problem/ problems in the village. To rectify these problems various techniques were implemented by government and non-government organizations.

PRACTICAL APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVE WATER MANAGEMENT:

After the identification of the problem at rural areas next step is to fix the problem. Further, it is estimated that 70% of worldwide water use is for irrigation, with 15-35% of irrigation withdrawals being unsustainable. It takes around 2,000 - 3,000 liters of water to produce enough food to satisfy one person's daily dietary need. In the future, even more water will be needed to produce food because the Earth's population is forecast to rise to 9 billion by 2050 [7]. This data highlights the importance of water management technique at rural and urban level. These techniques assured drought proofing, stabilized agriculture and improvement in living standard and provide good health to villagers. Major portion of water is used for

agriculture. To enhance the production and to ensure sustainable agriculture specific techniques are used to conserve rain water.

1 Watershed Development: Watershed Development is the first most practical technique used for the overall development of a village. The concept of watershed management has evolved to ensure effective use of both natural and social capitals.

Thus, the watershed development programmes include land, water and human resources as essential components.. The physical and climatic conditions in India vary to a large extent. The watershed programme is primarily a land based programme, which is increasingly being focused on water, with its main objective being to enhance agricultural productivity through increased in situ moisture conservation and protective irrigation for socio-economic development of rural people [8]. The importance of healthy watersheds is explained by John Wesley Powell, scientist geographer: “that area of land, a bounded hydrologic system, within which all living things are inextricably linked by their common water course and where, as humans settled, simple logic demanded that they become part of a community”. Watershed development has raised living standard of the people in many villages. Figure shows the sub techniques of watershed involved in agriculture [9].

One of the very important parameter of watershed development is Irrigation. It is the artificial application of water to the land or soil and is used to assist in the growing of agricultural crops, maintenance of landscapes, and revegetation of disturbed soils in dry areas and during periods of inadequate rainfall. In addition to this irrigation also helps in protection of plants from frost [10]. Irrigation techniques are subdivided in to three basic types such as lift

Irrigation, drip irrigation and sprinklers. In case of lift irrigation, water is required to be lifted at a convenient higher spot from which it can be supplied to the fields under command. Water can be lifted from wells, rivers, irrigation tanks etc. and conveyed through pipes made of cement, steel, PVC etc. Drip irrigation is easily used by the farmers. Small holes are created in the pipe so that wastage of excess water is prevented. In sprinkler Irrigation, at a distance of 6” to 2 feet pipes are converted into showers so that wastage of water become minimize. Center pivot irrigation is a form of sprinkler irrigation consisting of several segments of pipe (usually galvanized steel or aluminum) joined together and supported by trusses, mounted on wheeled towers with sprinklers positioned along its length [11,12]. The system moves in a circular pattern and is fed with water from the pivot point at the center of the arc.

2. Water Purification: This very important concept comes under Water management approach at Domestic level. The unsafe drinking water is a major problem in rural area and to provide drinking water to such a large population is an enormous challenge. It is estimated that around 37.7 million Indians are affected by waterborne diseases annually, 1.5 million children are estimated to die of diarrhoea alone and 73 million working days are lost due to waterborne disease each year. The resulting economic burden is estimated at \$600 million a year. The problems of chemical contamination are also prevalent in India with 1,95,813 habitations in the country are affected by poor water quality [13-15]. The major chemical parameters of concern are fluoride and arsenic. Iron is also emerging as a major problem with many habitations showing excess iron in the water samples. Due to unhygienic conditions the water gets contaminated and results in the various diseases related to bacterial infection. Bacterial contamination of water continues to be a widespread problem across the country and is a major cause of illness and deaths with 37.7 million affected by waterborne diseases annually. An emerging threat to water quality is due to the use of persistent organic pollutants (POPs). These are chemicals that degrade very slowly and remain in the environment for years. POPs accumulate in the fat tissue of organisms once exposed which meant that they are not excreted from the body. The POPs used widely in India are DDT, with an annual consumption of 10,000 Metric Tonnes; polychlorinated biphenyls used widely in capacitors and transformers and dioxins and furans used in the cement and pipe industry. Ground water in some locations in

Jharkhand, West Bengal, Himachal Pradesh and Delhi have reported levels of DDT, aldrin, dieldrin and heptachlor that are in excess of prescribed standards. It is the rural population that suffers the most of the problems related to fluoride, arsenic as well as microbial contamination. This clearly highlights the importance of water purification in rural areas.

In general the methods used for purification include physical processes such as filtration, sedimentation, and distillation, biological processes such as slow sand filters or biologically active carbon, chemical processes such as flocculation and chlorination and the use of electromagnetic radiation such as ultraviolet light. Simple technologies that are easy to use and can be operated without much technical know-how must be promoted. Traditional methods of water purification, in India, includes the use of natural coagulants like kataka seed, drumsticks, khas; water purifier with antibacterial an insecticidal properties such as tulsi, neem etc. in addition to this copper vessels are generally used which inhibits the bacterial growth. Water purification can be carried out at the household level and at the community level.

3. Waste Water Management is another important method of water management at domestic level. Waste water, is any water that has been adversely affected in quality by anthropogenic influence. Its management is an important component of sanitation activities. It is estimated and experienced that about 75% to 80% of water supplied through piped water supply schemes comes out as grey water. In rural areas, the major quantity of grey water is generated in a home. When this water leaves the premises of the house, it becomes community grey water.

4. Rain Water Harvesting is significant method of water management. It is the process of collection of rainwater from surfaces on which rain falls, filtering it and storing it for multiple uses. Rainwater harvesting puts the supply of water back to normal levels. It is the collection and storage of water from surfaces that rain has fallen upon. In a normal scenario the rainwater is

collected from roof buildings and then stored inside of a special tank. This water can be used externally like bathing , washing cloths etc. the water through the rains water harvesting can also used for drinking purpose by installing filter.

CONCLUSION:

Effective use of land and water is fundamental to growth and sustainable development. The importance of water has been recognized and the emphasis is being laid on its economic use and better management at rural areas. Moreover 68% of the total population of India lives in the villages and thus development of our villages is of critical importance for the economic development of the country. At the grass root level, to identify the exact problem of the concerned area by different approaches like PRA, problem and solution tree, questionnaire is very effective. These domestic and agriculture problems can be easily rectified by the measures like watershed techniques, water purification, waste water management and rain water harvesting. Successful implementation of such techniques results in social as well as economic upliftment of the villagers. These methods also contribute in good health of the villagers. Thus, in short, sustainable development through water management at villages plays an important role in maintaining the ecological balance and wellbeing of human society.

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